

Discriminating bladder cancer cells through rheological mechanomarkers at cell and spheroid levels

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ABSTRACT

The stiffening or softening of cancers observed in nanoindentation experiments has been recognized as a marker of cancer-related changes. In bladder cancers, continuous stretching/destretching is observed due to its functionality, indicating that shear forces dominate the mechanical response of these cells. Thus, nanoindentation and microrheological measurements conducted in parallel allow for a fully reliable mechanomarker of cancer progression. Here, bladder cancer cell lines, i.e., non-malignant cell cancer of the ureter (HCV29), bladder carcinoma (HT1376), and transitional cell carcinoma (T24), were studied. Nanoindentation and microrheological experiments were conducted on individual cells, cell monolayers, and spheroids that were formed using non-adherent surface plates. The results show that nanoindentation experiments can only differentiate between non-malignant HCV29 (stiffer) and cancerous HT1376 and T24 (softer) cells. Applying microrheology recognizes the type of grade 3 bladder cancers (carcinoma HT1376 or transitional cell carcinoma T24 cells). We showed that actin filaments are a vital element defining the rheological properties of spheroids. Differences in mechanical properties of cell monolayers could be associated with thick actin bundles and intercellular connections, with some extracellular matrix (ECM) contributing to the stiffening of such monolayers. Our findings demonstrate that a complete image of how cancer cells respond to mechanical stress (compressive and shear forces) can only be obtained after microrheological measurements using the transition frequency separating elastic and viscous regimes as a non-labeled biomarker of bladder cancer progression.

1. Introduction

Almost 90 % of bladder cancer is caused by the urothelial cells exposed to mutagenic agents sent from the kidney into the urine (Saginala et al., 2020; Sanli et al., 2017). Cancer progression alters, among others, cellular growth, differentiation, and interactions of cells with the extracellular matrix (ECM) and the adjacent cells (Armingol et al., 2021; Garcia et al., 2018; Giancotti, 2014). The invasion and metastasis are related to changes in the mechanical/rheological properties of cells (Hanahan and Weinberg, 2011; Suresh, 2007; Wang et al., 2021), followed by rearrangements in the actin cytoskeleton (Jain et al., 2014; Ridley et al., 2003; Weder et al., 2014; Yamaguchi and Condeelis, 2007). 3D spheroids have been widely applied as tumor models because they mimic the environment of cells and some essential features of solid tumors, such as cell–cell signaling, cell–matrix interactions, and drug resistance mechanism (Weiswald et al., 2015). There is little information regarding their biophysical properties, especially for bladder cancers.

Atomic force microscopy (AFM) is a versatile and powerful tool that unravels the relation between cellular structures and mechanical properties (Alessandrini and Facci, 2005; Rico et al., 2005; Sokolov, 2007). The technique has been used to study the elastic properties of cells originating from various cancers such as ovarian, breast, prostate, and thyroid, showing that cancer cells are softer (Canetta et al., 2014; Faria et al., 2008; Lekka et al., 2019, 2012; Li et al., 2008; Liu et al., 2014; Plodinec et al., 2012; Prabhune et al., 2012; Ramos et al., 2014; Wang et al., 2019; Xu et al., 2012). Cells are a complex viscoelastic material characterized by elastic and viscous contributions (Abidine et al., 2015; Lim et al., 2006; Nguyen et al., 2020; Northcott et al., 2018; Rebelo et al., 2013; Rother et al., 2014; Tse et al., 2012). The power-law rheological model, stemming from the soft glassy rheology theory (Sollich, 1998), suggests that the contraction and remodeling of the cytoskeleton is the reason behind the rheological behavior of the cells (Efremov et al., 2019, 2017). So far, there have been only a few research, in which AFM characterized the biomechanics of the spheroids focused

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mainly on their elasticity but not on rheology (Blumlein et al., 2017; Chaudhuri et al., 2020; Conrad et al., 2019; Giannetti et al., 2020; Guillaume et al., 2019; Vyas et al., 2019). Studying the microrheology of spheroids can answer several questions related to tissue mechanics and remodeling that are still less explored at the nanoscale.

Here, we compared the mechanical (compressive) and rheological (shear) properties of bladder cancer cells in a system mimicking the transition from non-malignant to invasive bladder cancers. Three distinct bladder cell lines that were derived from various stages of cancer progression were chosen for this study, i.e., non-malignant HCV29 cells derived from the non-cancerous part of the bladder carcinoma resembling the morphology and properties of the normal epithelium; non-invasive HT1376 cells (grade III bladder carcinoma), and invasive T24 cells (grade III, transitional cell carcinoma). The specific organization of the actin cytoskeleton characterizes the studied cells. HCV29 cells possess well-organized actin filaments with the abundant presence of actin bundles. In T24 cells, the thick actin bundles are less pronounced but still present. In HT1376 cells, there is no their presence. Since actin filaments are major cytoskeletal elements responsible for the single cell resistance to deformations, we hypothesize that their contribution is also significant in the mechanical/rheological properties of spheroids formed from the studied cells.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Cell lines and spheroids

Three human bladder cancer cell lines were used in this study: HCV29 – non-malignant transitional epithelial cancer cell of the ureter (O'Toole et al., 1974, 1973), obtained from the Institute of Experimental Therapy, PAN, Wrocław, Poland), T24 – transitional cell carcinoma (Bubeník et al., 1973), from ATCC, LGC Standards) and HT1376 – grade III urinary bladder cell carcinoma (Rasheed et al., 1977), from ATCC, LGC Standards). Spheroids were prepared in 96-well U-bottom 3D cell culture plates (ThermoFisher). The initial seeding density of cells/well was adjusted differently to the three cell lines set to obtain spheroids of 350–400 μm diameter after 3 days of incubation. Details are described in [Supplementary Information – S1. Materials and methods.](#)

2.2. Characterizing morphology, mechanical and rheological properties of cells and spheroids

The morphology of cells and spheroids in 2D and 3D cultures was characterized using the Western blot technique (G/F actin content), epifluorescence, and confocal microscopy. Mechanical and rheological properties were measured using a commercial AFM (Xe120 model, Park Systems, Korea) working in a force spectroscopy mode and integrated with an inverted optical microscope (Olympus IX71) and Nanowizard IV (Bruker – JPK Instruments), also coupled to an inverted optical microscope (Olympus IX71). The former was applied for nanoindentation, while the latter measured rheological properties using the Micro-Rheology module. Details are described in [Supplementary Information – S1. Materials and Methods.](#)

2.3. Statistics.

The nanomechanical and microrheological data analysis was conducted on fully independent data sets. The means value was calculated for each elasticity map, and such data were used to create all plots. Thus, every single dot denotes a single elasticity map. In the case of cells, one elasticity map was recorded for one cell. Finally, the data are presented as a mean \pm standard error (SEM). Statistical significance was obtained using a non-parametric Mann-Whitney test at the significance level of 0.05.

3. Results

3.1. Different monomeric G-actin content combined with the reorganization of actin filaments confirmed cytoskeletal changes in bladder cancer cells

Mechanical and rheological properties are typically related to the organization of the actin cytoskeleton (Lekka, 2016). In the first step of our study, we collected fluorescent images of actin filaments (phalloidin – Alexa Fluor 488 dye for F-actin (Estes et al., 1981)), for individual, isolated cells, monolayers, and spheroids (Fig. 1A-C). HCV29 cells resemble the morphology of normal urothelium. Cells were elongated with clearly visible long and thick actin bundles spanning a whole cell, probably stress fibers (Gavara and Chadwick, 2016). The number of actin bundles increases significantly for cells forming a monolayer. Cancer cells were different. T24 cells were more roundish with fewer long actin fibers than HCV29 cells. HT1376 cells did not show any actin fibers regardless of the culture conditions (individual cells or monolayer). Their actin cytoskeleton appeared as a more homogeneous structure. The thick actin bundles were more pronounced in HCV29 than in T24 cells and not detectable in HT1376 cells. This relation remains unaltered in both single cells and cell monolayers. Next, we ask how the actin cytoskeleton is organized in spheroids composed of these cells. Actin filaments form a sheath surrounding the cell interior (mostly cell nucleus), inside which thick actin bundles are not visible (Fig. 1C). The clarity of the actin sheaths depends on cell types. Sheaths are visible in carcinoma HT1376 and non-malignant HCV29 cells, while they are barely visible in transitional carcinoma T24 cells, in which regions with brighter fluorescent signals denote high F-actin concentrations.

In cells, actin is present in monomeric G-actin and polymerized F-actin forms (Dominguez and Holmes, 2011). A few studies reported that the deformability and invasiveness of cancer cells depend on the actin or myosin content (Gavara and Chadwick, 2016; Xu et al., 2012). We postulate that a large amount of G-actin monomers contributes to the viscous part of the cells. G- and F-actin expression was estimated from the Western blot by applying the densitometry approach (Fig. 1D). The highest G/F ratio (3.74 ± 0.74 , $n = 3$) was obtained for HT1376 cells. It was 2–3 times higher than in the case of HCV29 (2.04 ± 0.34 , $n = 4$) and T24 (1.12 ± 0.08 , $n = 4$) cells, which indicated a greater level of G-actin monomers inside these cells. It correlates with the actin cytoskeleton organization characterized by actin mesh without thick actin bundles. To evaluate the magnitude of changes, the $\log_{10}(G_to_F_{cancer}/G_to_F_{HCV29})$ was calculated in relation to reference, non-malignant HCV29 cells (referred here to score index, Fig. 1F). The score index shows that the amount of G-actin decreases (T24 cells) and increases (HT1376 cells) to the same extent.

3.2. The role of actin filaments in cell mechanics remained unaltered regardless of their 2D or 3D organization

As already published, single bladder cancer cells are softer than non-malignant cells (Ramos et al., 2014; Zemla et al., 2020). Here, we pose the further question, i.e., to what extent do intercellular connections and ECM matrix affect the capability of the AFM-based nanoindentation measurements to recognize cancerous cells. To answer, nanoindentation experiments were conducted on single, isolated cells, 2D cell monolayers, and 3D spheroids (the principle of the AFM nanoindentation experiment is schematically shown in Fig. 2A&B). We assumed that contributions stemming from actin cytoskeleton and intercellular connections would be the main reason for the mechanical properties of cells organized in monolayers and spheroids. In the case of the latter, an additional contribution from the presence of ECM was expected (Fig. 2C). The AFM-based elasticity measurements showed that, similarly to single cell level, monolayers formed from HCV29 cells are more rigid than monolayers formed from cancer cells (Fig. 2D, distributions are presented in [Suppl. Fig. S1](#)). The apparent Young's modulus

Fig. 1. Bladder cancer cells display distinct actin filaments organization accompanied by altered expression of monomeric G-actin. Cells (non-malignant HCV29, transitional carcinoma T24, and carcinoma HT1376 cells) were cultured as single isolated cells (A) or 2D monolayers (B) or 3D spheroids (C, one slice from the Z-stacks is shown). F-actin was stained using phalloidin – Alexa Fluor 488 (green) in all cases. Cell nuclei were stained with Hoechst 33,342 dyes (blue, A, B, epifluorescent microscopy) or SiR-DNA (red, C, confocal microscopy). Scale bars = 10 μ m. (D) Exemplary results from Western blot show the content of monomeric G-actin and polymerized F-actin in bladder cells. The used antibody (against β -actin) targets all known actin isoforms with a molecular mass of 43 kDa (globular actin and fibrous actin). (E) G/F ratio was obtained from densitometry for non-malignant HCV29 cells, transitional carcinoma T24 cells, and carcinoma HT1376 cells (data are expressed as a mean \pm SEM, from 3 to 4 independent repetitions, $**p < 0.001$). Notably, the ratio is smaller for cells displaying thick actin bundles. (F) The score index showing that, in relation to reference, non-malignant HCV29 cells, the amount of G-actin decreases (T24 cells) and increases (HT1376 cells) to the same extent. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

increased from 6.8 ± 0.5 kPa (single cells, mean \pm SEM; $n = 55$ cells measured) to 16.5 ± 1.0 kPa (monolayers, $n = 45$ cells). A similar increment was observed for T24 cells, for which elastic moduli raised from 2.7 ± 0.2 kPa (single cells, $n = 64$ cells) to 13.0 ± 0.9 kPa (monolayers, $n = 52$ cells). On the contrary, the elastic modulus for HT1376 cells remained at the same level of 5.3 ± 0.4 kPa (single cells, $n = 58$ cells) and 5.3 ± 0.3 kPa (monolayers, $n = 27$ cells). Notably, the increase of Young's modulus is observed in only cells displaying thick actin bundles (HCV29 and T24 cells), but it is not correlated with the G/F actin ratio. The stiffening of monolayers can be explained by reorganizing actin bundles and intercellular connections. Although bladder cancer cell lines (like T24 cells) do not express E-cadherins (Lekka et al., 2011), our previous data showed that E-cadherins switch to N-cadherins (Lekka et al., 2011), thus enabling the cellular connections through indirect links involvement of actin filaments (Mège and Ishiyama, 2017). The lack of thick actin bundles in carcinoma HT1376 cells weakens the contribution from intercellular connections; thus, the mechanical properties response in these cells is mainly governed by the actin cortex.

Hereafter, we measured the mechanical properties of multicellular spheroids formed by the same bladder cell lines (Fig. 2E). As we would like to obtain the value that reveals the mechanics of cells embedded within the spheroid microenvironment to sense ECM contribution, the indentation depth of 2–3 μ m was applied in the AFM measurements. The results showed that spheroids consisting of HCV29 cells were the stiffest, with an elastic modulus of 14.5 ± 2.2 kPa ($n = 25$ maps, recorded for 15 spheroids). Spheroids made of cancer cells were characterized by a

lower modulus of 2.7 ± 0.3 kPa ($n = 27$ maps for 15 spheroids) and 2.4 ± 0.2 kPa ($n = 28$ maps for 15 spheroids), respectively for T24 and HT1376 cells. Notably, a comparable elastic modulus indicates a similar response of spheroids to compressive forces.

The main problem in the AFM measurements is the relativeness of the modulus, which has already been discussed, e.g. (Lekka et al., 2012). To be independent of the experimental conditions and to compare measurements recorded with different cantilevers, we introduce the rigidity index R , defined as a moduli ratio of cancer to a reference sample. The rigidity index, analogously to the viscoelasticity index (Sobiepanek et al., 2022), can be used as a marker of mechanical changes related to the cancer stage. Its value significantly deviating from zero indicates large changes in cell biomechanics due to cancer. Our findings show that cancer-related changes lead to cell softening regardless of their 2D or 3D organization (Fig. 2F). The maximum softening was observed for the spheroids containing either T24 or HT1376 cells ($R = -0.75$ and -0.85 , for T24 and HT1376, respectively). This indicates that HCV29 cells are highly rigid even when organized as spheroids. Simultaneously, its value shows that not all measurement conditions are suitable for identifying cancer cells (rigidity index is close to zero).

3.3. Independently measured microrheological properties of bladder cancer cells show bladder cancer softening at the single-cell and spheroid levels

Contact mechanics used to determine Young's modulus assumes that

Fig. 2. Bladder cancers soften regardless of the culture conditions, as revealed from AFM-based nanoindentation experiments. (A) Schematic representation of the AFM-based elasticity experiments, accompanied by top-view images of the experimental setups used to measure cells and spheroids. Two distinct cantilevers were used: MLCT-D (for 2D cell cultures) and NSC36-C (used for spheroids). (B) The elastic (Young's modulus) is calculated as a difference between force curves recorded for rigid and compliant materials. During indentation, force curves were recorded over the nuclear region (cells) or in the central part of the spheroids, within the scan area of $64 \mu\text{m}^2$ (a map of 6 pixels per 6 pixels was set; 36 force curves were collected for single cells). (C) Illustration of the actin cytoskeleton, intercellular connections, and ECM contributions to the overall mechanical properties at different culture conditions. (D) Box plots showing Young's modulus variability for 2D cultured conditions, i.e., single, isolated cells and monolayers. Each point denotes the mean value calculated for a single cell. The total number of cells measured was between 27 and 50 cells, depending on the cell type and culture conditions. The black dots and lines are the mean and median, respectively; the box denotes standard deviation; error bars represent the 10 % and 90 % percentile. (E) Analogous comparison between spheroids composed of normal and cancer cells. 15 spheroids were measured for each cell line (2 force maps/spheroid, each point denotes an individual elasticity map). (*** $p < 0.001$, ns – not statistically significant). (F) The rigidity index shows the degree of cancer cell softening in relation to non-malignant HCV29 cells, depending on the culture conditions (single cells, monolayers, and spheroids). The largest softening was observed for spheroids.

living cells are purely elastic materials with high structural homogeneity. Cells are not fulfilling this assumption because they reveal a viscoelastic nature (de Sousa et al., 2020; Rother et al., 2014). Cell softening indicated by negative values of the rigidity index can supposedly be related to the larger fluidity of cancer cells (Aermes et al., 2021; Alibert et al., 2017). Thus, in our next steps, microrheological measurements were conducted in the frequency domain (Fig. 3A) by applying sine oscillations with the amplitude of 50 nm at the indentation depth of $1 \mu\text{m}$ (for single cells and monolayers) and $2.5 \mu\text{m}$ (for spheroids). The calculated storage G' and loss G'' moduli were plotted as a function of oscillation frequency ω (Fig. 3B) and fitted with the power-law functions (Abidine et al., 2015). A set of microrheology parameters was determined, i.e., storage G_N' and loss G_N'' shear moduli, loss factor, transition frequency ω_T , and power-law exponent α (Supplementary Table S1). Storage modulus G_N' , related to the elastic energy stored in the measured sample, describes a storage shear modulus G' value at $\omega = 0$. It correlates with Young's modulus (Fig. 3C). The relation follows the classical relation $G = E/(1 + \nu)$ with $\nu = 0.5$ (incompressible materials). A slope of 3.414 ± 0.762 was obtained (Pearsons' coefficient describing the quality of the fit was 0.86109).

Several conclusions can be drawn from the relations between storage (loss) modulus measured in a frequency domain (Fig. 3D-L). Storage modulus is the highest for single non-malignant HCV29 cells, indicating higher shear forces resistance. Lower storage modulus obtained for cancer cells indicated larger cellular deformability induced by shear forces. Analogously, the loss shear modulus G_N'' , which corresponds to the dissipated energy in the sample, describes G'' value at $\omega = 0$, and it is lower than G' for low frequencies. It is larger for non-malignant and lower for cancerous ones, and it seems to be independent of how cells are organized. By calculating the loss factor, G_N''/G_N' we would assess the behavior of non-malignant and cancerous cells. The average overall loss factor ($n = 3$, loss factors obtained for single cells, monolayers, and spheroids) equals 0.21 ± 0.05 , 0.28 ± 0.07 , and 0.38 ± 0.16 for HCV29,

T24, and HT1376 cells, respectively. A higher loss factor suggests a shift towards the fluid-like regime. Thus, cancer cells are more viscous than non-malignant cells.

3.4. Cytochalasin D reveals the link between the presence of actin fibers and the storage modulus, but not the loss modulus

In the next step, the cells from 2D cultures and spheroids were treated with $5 \mu\text{M}$ cytochalasin D (cyto D), a permeable toxin that inhibits the polymerization of actin filaments (Cooper, 1987). The effect of cytochalasin D on mechanical properties is also known for bladder cancer cells (Lekka et al., 2001; Ramos et al., 2014); therefore, we focused on evaluating its effect on the rheological properties of cells. The first observation is that, regardless of the cell type, a drop of storage modulus appears above 10–20 Hz (Fig. 3). As the actin cytoskeleton is disrupted, individual cells lose their attachment to the surface, leading to lower resistance to shear forces and probably easier detachment; despite that, the full detachment of cyto D-treated cells was not observed. Such an effect is not observed in spheroids because removing single cells from a 3D environment is more challenging even for high frequencies (maximum applied modulation frequency was set to 250 Hz, and no hydrodynamic drag correction was applied). Simultaneously, the effect of cyto D on spheroids was visible in confocal images (Fig. 4A). The loss factor and power-law exponent show considerable variability, which is difficult to be correlated with changes in the actin cytoskeleton before and after treatment with cyto D (Supplementary Table S1).

3.5. Fluidization of bladder cancer cells is better identified by a lower transition frequency, not by a higher power-law exponent

Next, we asked how well we could detect the transition between solid-like and fluid-like regimes of cells. Thus, we analyzed the transition frequency ω_T and compared it to the power-law exponent α . The

Fig. 3. Applied shear deformation and resulting complex modulus reveal a distinct mechanism of bladder cancer cell softening. (A) AFM-based microrheology. A sine modulation was applied at the indentation of 1 μm (single cells and monolayers) and 2.5 μm (for spheroids) with the amplitude of 50 nm applied to probe the local microenvironment of the probing tip. The resulting oscillations in the vertical cantilever deflection served as a basis for shear modulus determination. Sine modulations were recorded for frequencies from 1 Hz to 100 Hz (2D cultures) and from 1 Hz to 250 Hz (spheroids), taken from the central cell or spheroid regions. (B) Storage G' and loss modulus G'' plotted as a function of oscillation frequency ω . Lines represent fits of the power-law functions to the obtained data. A transition frequency differentiating between elastic and viscous regimes was calculated as a crossover of these two curves. (C) A linear regression of Young's and shear moduli (Pearson's coefficient $R = 0.8609$). The slope of 3.414 corresponds to the theoretical slope of 3 (for Poisson's ratio for cells equals 0.5). (D-L) Microrheological data for bladder cancer cells (HCV29, T24, and HT1376 cells). Each point denotes the mean \pm standard error of the mean from $n = 30$ to 40 cells (2D cultures) or 15 spheroids from each cell line (2 maps/spheroid). Black squares represent control, non-treated cells, while red dots show rheological data of cells treated with cyto D. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

obtained results show that the transition frequency decreases for cancer cells, indicating fluidization of cells (Fig. 4B, Supplementary Table S1). Power-law exponents for bladder cancer cells were cell type-dependent (Fig. 4C). Its larger value indicates a shift towards the fluid-like behavior of cancer cells. This matches with the low transition frequency obtained for cancer cells.

To evaluate the contribution of actin filaments in the fluidization of cells, transition frequency and power-law exponent were determined for cyto D-treated cells (Fig. 4BC). The transition frequency for cyto D-treated cells becomes significantly lower than the untreated cells, except

for spheroids made of HT1376 cells. Cyto D alters the power-law exponent, but these changes are less conclusive. The negative rigidity index indicates that the softening of cyto D-treated cells depends on the culture conditions and cell type (Fig. 4D). A subsequent decrease in the rigidity index (largest for single cells, lowest for spheroids) indicates ECM contributes to the microrheological properties. After cyto D, a shift towards a smaller rigidity index suggested that ECM induces cell stiffening, indicating its contribution to the microrheological properties of cancer cells.

Fig. 4. Cytochalasin D (cyto D) demonstrated that F-actin is responsible for changes in the rheological properties of bladder cancer cells. Cyto D prevented the polymerization of F-actin in spheroids. Confocal image of F-actin stained with phalloidin conjugated with Alexa Fluor 488 dye (magnification 63x). (B) Transition frequency ω_T (a crossover between $G'(\omega)$ and $G''(\omega)$), and (C) power-law exponent (α), determined for the control and cyto D (5 μ M) treated cells. (D) Rigidity index, calculated analogously as for Young's modulus.

4. Discussion

The measurements of Young's modulus by AFM have already been used as a relevant method to distinguish cancerous cells (Lekka et al., 2012; Mège, 2019). It has been demonstrated that the mechanical properties of cells are mainly dependent on the cytoskeleton structure, particularly on actin filaments that could be reorganized by actomyosin stress fibers changing the internal stress (Gavara and Chadwick, 2016; Lehtimäki et al., 2021). Actin filaments behave like viscoelastic materials (Grosser et al., 2021; Rigato et al., 2017), thus, both elastic and viscous components must be considered to obtain a complete description of cell mechanics. The single bladder cancer cells have already been measured in AFM-based nanoindentation experiments, showing that the non-malignant cells are stiffer than the cancer cells (Abidine et al., 2021, 2015; Canetta et al., 2014; Lekka et al., 2019; Ramos et al., 2014). We pose the further question, i.e., to what extent do intercellular connections and ECM matrix affect the capability of the AFM-based nanoindentation measurements to recognize cancerous cells.

In our experiments, the nanomechanical (compressive) and rheological (shear) properties of cells were assessed for non-malignant cell cancer of the ureter (HCV29 cells) and bladder cancers. Carcinoma HT1376 and transitional cell carcinoma T24 cells mimic grade 3 bladder cancers of low and high invasiveness (Vasyutin et al., 2019; Wu et al., 2014). We found out that the overall elastic properties of cells are not affected by the culture conditions (single cells, monolayers, or spheroids). The non-malignant HCV29 cells formed stiffer spheroids than cancer cells making Young's modulus a potential biomechanical marker of bladder cancers. However, its value permits only to distinguish of non-malignant cells from cancerous cells. Non-invasive grade 3 (HT1376 cells) and invasive grade 3 (T24 cells) cancers are indistinguishable. By applying microrheology that measures the response to shear forces (Alcaraz et al., 2003), it was possible to differentiate between these cancer types.

Stiffening of HCV29 and T24 cells during monolayer cultures and no changes observed for the biomechanics of HT1376 cells were associated with the presence and absence of thick actin bundles accompanied by intercellular connections. Analogous rigidity increase was observed for spheroids composed of HCV29 and T24 cells (i.e., the storage modulus is larger for spheroids than for single cells). On the contrary, HT1376 cells

become softer. These results indicate that thick actin bundles also contribute to the mechanical resistance of cells to shear stress, both at the cellular and spheroid levels.

Mechanically induced fluidization of cells was quantified better via the transition frequency from solid-like to fluid-like behaviors (Grosser et al., 2021; Mège, 2019). Our results show that HCV29 cells have the highest transition frequency, compared to T24 and HT1376 cells, regardless of the culture conditions. In these non-malignant HCV29 cells, the transition frequency increases when passing from single cells to spheroids. A similar but smaller increase was observed for T24 cells as well. Unlike HCV29 and T24, the carcinoma HT1376 cells have a different cytoskeletal structure, and consequently, the absence of thick actin bundles does not modify the viscoelastic properties when the confluency is altered. Therefore, we could explain these effects with the presence of thick actin bundles in these cells.

In conclusion, we aimed to establish a quantitative measure to classify cancer cells at different progression stages, assuming that compressive and shear stress drive cells towards a more invasive phenotype characterized by larger deformability of cancer cells. Introduced here rigidity index allows us to objectively evaluate the biomechanical and rheological changes, regardless of the culture conditions. Our findings show that the organization of actin filaments is responsible for biomechanics and rheology at the cellular and spheroid levels. Intercellular connections and ECM contribute to cell mechanics and rheology, but the role of actin filaments remains unaltered. Overall, softening and fluidization of bladder cancer spheroids, connected with cancer progression, seems to be linked with the remodelling of actin filaments.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Kajangi Gnanachandran: Writing – original draft, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Sylwia Kędracka-Krok:** Validation, Investigation. **Joanna Pabijan:** Investigation. **Małgorzata Lekka:** Writing – original draft, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial

interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbiomech.2022.111346>.

References

- Abidine, Y., Laurent, V.M., Michel, R., Duperray, A., Verdier, C., 2015. Local mechanical properties of bladder cancer cells measured by AFM as a signature of metastatic potential. *Eur. Phys. J. Plus* 130, 202. <https://doi.org/10.1140/epjp/i2015-15202-6>.
- Abidine, Y., Giannetti, A., Revilloud, J., Laurent, V.M., Verdier, C., 2021. Viscoelastic properties in cancer: From cells to spheroids. *Cells* 10, 1074. <https://doi.org/10.3390/cells10071704>.
- Aermes, C., Hayn, A., Fischer, T., Mierke, C.T., 2021. Cell mechanical properties of human breast carcinoma cells depend on temperature. *Sci. Rep.* 11, 10771. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-021-90173-y>.
- Alcaraz, J., Buscemi, L., Grabulosa, M., Trepast, X., Fabry, B., Farré, R., Navajas, D., 2003. Microrheology of human lung epithelial cells measured by atomic force microscopy. *Biophys. J.* 84, 2071–2079. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0006-3495\(03\)75014-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0006-3495(03)75014-0).
- Alessandrini, A., Facci, P., 2005. AFM: A versatile tool in biophysics. *Meas. Sci. Technol.* 16 (6), R65–R92.
- Alibert, C., Goud, B., Manneville, J.B., 2017. Are cancer cells really softer than normal cells? *Biol. Cell.* 109, 167–189. <https://doi.org/10.1111/boc.201600078>.
- Armingol, E., Officer, A., Harismendy, O., Lewis, N.E., 2021. Deciphering cell–cell interactions and communication from gene expression. *Nat. Rev. Genet.* 22, 71–88. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41576-020-00292-x>.
- Blumlein, A., Williams, N., McManus, J.J., 2017. The mechanical properties of individual cell spheroids. *Sci. Rep.* 7, 7346. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-017-07813-5>.
- Bubenik, J., Barešová, M., Viklický, V., Jakoubková, J., Sainerová, H., Donner, J., 1973. Established cell line of urinary bladder carcinoma (T24) containing tumour-specific antigen. *Int. J. Cancer* 11, 765–773. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ijc.2910110327>.
- Canetta, E., Riches, A., Borger, E., Herrington, S., Dholakia, K., Adya, A.K., 2014. Discrimination of bladder cancer cells from normal urothelial cells with high specificity and sensitivity: Combined application of atomic force microscopy and modulated Raman spectroscopy. *Acta Biomater.* 10, 2043–2055. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actbio.2013.12.057>.
- Chaudhuri, O., Cooper-White, J., Jamney, P.A., Mooney, D.J., Shenoy, V.B., 2020. Effects of extracellular matrix viscoelasticity on cellular behaviour. *Nature* 584, 535–546. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-020-2612-2>.
- Conrad, C., Gray, K.M., Stroka, K.M., Rizvi, I., Scarcelli, G., 2019. Mechanical characterization of 3D ovarian cancer nodules using Brillouin confocal microscopy. *Cell. Mol. Bioeng.* 12, 215–226. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12195-019-00570-7>.
- Cooper, J.A., 1987. Effects of cytochalasin and phalloidin on actin. *J. Cell Biol.* 105, 1473–1478. <https://doi.org/10.1083/jcb.105.4.1473>.
- de Sousa, J.S., Freire, R.S., Sousa, F.D., Radmacher, M., Silva, A.F.B., Ramos, M.V., Monteiro-Moreira, A.C.O., Mesquita, F.P., Moraes, M.E.A., Montenegro, R.C., Oliveira, C.L.N., 2020. Double power-law viscoelastic relaxation of living cells encodes motility trends. *Sci. Rep.* 10, 4749. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-020-61631-w>.
- Dominguez, R., Holmes, K.C., 2011. Actin structure and function. *Annu. Rev. Biophys.* 40, 169–186. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-biophys-042910-155359>.
- Efremov, Y.M., Wang, W.H., Hardy, S.D., Geahlen, R.L., Raman, A., 2017. Measuring nanoscale viscoelastic parameters of cells directly from AFM force-displacement curves. *Sci. Rep.* 7, 1541. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-017-01784-3>.
- Efremov, Y.M., Okajima, T., Raman, A., 2019. Measuring viscoelasticity of soft biological samples using atomic force microscopy. *Soft Matter* 16, 64–81. <https://doi.org/10.1039/c9sm01020c>.
- Estes, J.E., Selden, L.A., Gershman, L.C., 1981. Mechanism of action of phalloidin on the polymerization of muscle actin. *Biochemistry* 20, 708–712. <https://doi.org/10.1021/bi00507a006>.
- Faria, E.C., Ma, N., Gazi, E., Gardner, P., Brown, M., Clarke, N.W., Snook, R.D., 2008. Measurement of elastic properties of prostate cancer cells using AFM. *Analyst* 133, 1498–1500. <https://doi.org/10.1039/b803355b>.
- García, M.A., Nelson, W.J., Chavez, N., 2018. Cell–cell junctions organize structural and signaling networks. *Cold Spring Harb. Perspect. Biol.* 10 (4), a029181.
- Gavara, N., Chadwick, R.S., 2016. Relationship between cell stiffness and stress fiber amount, assessed by simultaneous atomic force microscopy and live-cell fluorescence imaging. *Biomech. Model. Mechanobiol.* 15, 511–523. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10237-015-0706-9>.
- Giancotti, F.G., 2014. Deregulation of cell signaling in cancer. *FEBS Lett.* 588, 2558–2570. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.febslet.2014.02.005>.
- Giannetti, A., Revilloud, J., Verdier, C., 2020. Mechanical properties of 3D tumor spheroids measured by AFM. *Comput. Methods Biomech. Biomed. Engin.* 23, S125–S127. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10255842.2020.1816297>.
- Grosser, S., Lippoldt, J., Oswald, L., Merkel, M., Sussman, D.M., Renner, F., Gotthel, P., Morawetz, E.W., Fuhs, T., Xie, X., Pawlizak, S., Fritsch, A.W., Wolf, B., Horn, L.C., Briest, S., Aktas, B., Manning, M.L., Kas, J.A., 2021. Cell and nucleus shape as an indicator of tissue fluidity in carcinoma. *Phys. Rev. X* 11, 011033. <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevX.11.011033>.
- Guillaume, L., Rigal, L., Fehrenbach, J., Severac, C., Ducommun, B., Lobjois, V., 2019. Characterization of the physical properties of tumor-derived spheroids reveals critical insights for pre-clinical studies. *Sci. Rep.* 9, 6597. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-019-43090-0>.
- Hanahan, D., Weinberg, R.A., 2011. Hallmarks of cancer: The next generation. *Cell* 144, 646–674. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cell.2011.02.013>.
- Jain, R.K., Martin, J.D., Stylianopoulos, T., 2014. The role of mechanical forces in tumor growth and therapy. *Annu. Rev. Biomed. Eng.* 16, 321–346. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-bioeng-071813-105259>.
- Lehtimäki, J.I., Rajakylä, E.K., Tojkander, S., Lappalainen, P., 2021. Generation of stress fibers through myosin-driven reorganization of the actin cortex. *Elife* 10, 1–43. <https://doi.org/10.7554/eLife.60710>.
- Lekka, M., 2016. Discrimination between normal and cancerous cells using AFM. *Bionanoscience* 6, 65–80. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12668-016-0191-3>.
- Lekka, M., Laidler, P., Ignacak, J.J., Labd, M., Lekki, J., Struszczyk, H., Stachura, Z., Hryniewicz, A.Z., 2001. The effect of chitosan on stiffness and glycolytic activity of human bladder cells. *Biochim. Biophys. Acta - Mol. Cell Res.* 1540, 127–136. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0167-4889\(01\)00125-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0167-4889(01)00125-2).
- Lekka, M., Gil, D., Dabros, W., Jaczewska, J., Kulik, A.J., Lekki, J., Stachura, Z., Stachura, J., Laidler, P., 2011. Characterization of N-cadherin unbinding properties in non-malignant (HCV29) and malignant (T24) bladder cells. *J. Mol. Recognit.* 24, 833–842. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jmr.1123>.
- Lekka, M., Pogoda, K., Gostek, J., Klymenko, O., Prauzner-Bechcicki, S., Wiltowska-Zuber, J., Jaczewska, J., Lekki, J., Stachura, Z., 2012. Cancer cell recognition - Mechanical phenotype. *Micron* 43, 1259–1266. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.micron.2012.01.019>.
- Lekka, M., Pabijan, J., Orzechowska, B., 2019. Morphological and mechanical stability of bladder cancer cells in response to substrate rigidity. *Biochim. Biophys. Acta - Gen. Subj.* 1863, 1006–1014. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bbagen.2019.03.010>.
- Li, Q.S., Lee, G.Y.H., Ong, C.N., Lim, C.T., 2008. AFM indentation study of breast cancer cells. *Biochem. Biophys. Res. Commun.* 374, 609–613. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bbrc.2008.07.078>.
- Lim, C.T., Zhou, E.H., Quek, S.T., 2006. Mechanical models for living cells - A review. *J. Biomech.* 39, 195–216. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbiomech.2004.12.008>.
- Liu, H., Wen, J., Xiao, Y., Liu, J., Hopyan, S., Radisic, M., Simmons, C.A., Sun, Y., 2014. In situ mechanical characterization of the cell nucleus by atomic force microscopy. *ACS Nano* 8, 3821–3828. <https://doi.org/10.1021/nm500553z>.
- Mège, R.M., 2019. Molecular basis for fluidization of cancer cells. *Nat. Mater.* 18, 1147–1148. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41563-019-0521-2>.
- Mège, R.M., Ishiyama, N., 2017. Integration of cadherin adhesion and cytoskeleton at adherens junctions. *Cold Spring Harb. Perspect. Biol.* 9 (5), a028738.
- Nguyen, T.L., Polanco, E.R., Patananan, A.N., Zangle, T.A., Teitell, M.A., 2020. Cell viscoelasticity is linked to fluctuations in cell biomass distributions. *Sci. Rep.* 10, 7403. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-020-64259-y>.
- Northcott, J.M., Dean, I.S., Mouw, J.K., Weaver, V.M., 2018. Feeling stress: The mechanics of cancer progression and aggression. *Front. Cell Dev. Biol.* 6, 17. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fcell.2018.00017>.
- O'Toole, C., Perlmann, P., Wigzell, H., Zetterlund, B.U.C.G., 1973. Lymphocyte cytotoxicity in bladder cancer no requirement for thymus-derived effector cells? *Lancet* 301, 1085–1088. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(73\)90396-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(73)90396-6).
- O'Toole, C., Stejskal, V., Perlmann, P., Karlsson, M., 1974. Lymphoid cells mediating tumor-specific cytotoxicity to carcinoma of the urinary bladder: Separation of the effector population using a surface marker. *J. Exp. Med.* 139, 457–466. <https://doi.org/10.1084/jem.139.3.457>.
- Plodinec, M., Lopic, M., Monnier, C.A., Obermann, E.C., Zanetti-Dallenbach, R., Oertle, P., Hyotyla, J.T., Aebi, U., Bentires-Alj, M., Lim, R.Y.H., Schoenberger, C.A., 2012. The nanomechanical signature of breast cancer. *Nat. Nanotechnol.* 7, 757–765. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nnano.2012.167>.
- Prabhune, M., Belge, G., Dotzauer, A., Bullerdiek, J., Radmacher, M., 2012. Comparison of mechanical properties of normal and malignant thyroid cells. *Micron* 43, 1267–1272. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.micron.2012.03.023>.
- Ramos, J.R., Pabijan, J., Garcia, R., Lekka, M., 2014. The softening of human bladder cancer cells happens at an early stage of the malignancy process. *Beilstein J. Nanotechnol.* 5, 447–457. <https://doi.org/10.3762/bjnano.5.52>.
- Rasheed, S., Gardner, M.B., Rongey, R.W., Nelson-Rees, W.A., Armstein, P., 1977. Human bladder carcinoma: Characterization of two new tumor cell lines and search for tumor viruses. *J. Natl. Cancer Inst.* 58, 881–890. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jnci/58.4.881>.
- Rebello, L.M., de Sousa, J.S., Mendes Filho, J., Radmacher, M., 2013. Comparison of the viscoelastic properties of cells from different kidney cancer phenotypes measured with atomic force microscopy. *Nanotechnology* 24 (5), 055102.
- Rico, F., Roca-Cusachs, P., Gavara, N., Farré, R., Rotger, M., Navajas, D., 2005. Probing mechanical properties of living cells by atomic force microscopy with blunted pyramidal cantilever tips. *Phys. Rev. E - Stat. Nonlinear, Soft Matter Phys.* 72, 0921914. <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevE.72.021914>.
- Ridley, A.J., Schwartz, M.A., Burridge, K., Firtel, R.A., Ginsberg, M.H., Borisy, G., Parsons, J.T., Horwitz, A.R., 2003. Cell migration: Integrating signals from front to back. *Science* 302 (5651), 1704–1709.
- Rigato, A., Miyagi, A., Scheuring, S., Rico, F., 2017. High-frequency microrheology reveals cytoskeleton dynamics in living cells. *Nat. Phys.* 13, 771–775. <https://doi.org/10.1038/NPHYS4104>.

- Rother, J., Nöding, H., Mey, I., Janshoff, A., 2014. Atomic force microscopy-based microrheology reveals significant differences in the viscoelastic response between malignant and benign cell lines. *Open Biol.* 4 (5), 140046.
- Saginala, K., Barsouk, A., Aluru, J.S., Rawla, P., Padala, S.A., Barsouk, A., 2020. Epidemiology of bladder cancer. *Med. Sci.* 8, 15.
- Sanli, O., Dobruch, J., Knowles, M.A., Burger, M., Alemezaffar, M., Nielsen, M.E., Lotan, Y., 2017. Bladder cancer. *Bladder cancer. Nat. Rev. Dis. Prim.* 3 (1), 170022 <https://doi.org/10.1038/nrdp.2017.22>.
- Sobiepanek, A., Kowalska, P.D., Szota, M., Grzywa, T.M., Nowak, J., Włodarski, P.K., Galus, R., Jachimska, B., Kobiela, T., 2022. Novel diagnostic and prognostic factors for the advanced melanoma based on the glycosylation-related changes studied by biophysical profiling methods. *Biosens. Bioelectron.* 203, 114046 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bios.2022.114046>.
- Sokolov, I., 2007. Atomic Force Microscopy in Cancer Cell Research, in: *Cancer Nanotechnology – Nanomaterials for Cancer Diagnosis and Therapy*. pp. 1–17.
- Sollich, P., 1998. Rheological constitutive equation for a model of soft glassy materials. *Phys. Rev. E - Stat. Physics, Plasmas, Fluids, Relat. Interdiscip. Top.* 58, 738–759. <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevE.58.738>.
- Suresh, S., 2007. Biomechanics and biophysics of cancer cells. *Acta Mater.* 55, 3989–4014. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actamat.2007.04.022>.
- Tse, J.M., Cheng, G., Tyrrell, J.A., Wilcox-Adelman, S.A., Boucher, Y., Jain, R.K., Munn, L.L., 2012. Mechanical compression drives cancer cells toward invasive phenotype. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* 109, 911–916. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1118910109>.
- Vasyutin, I., Zerihun, L., Ivan, C., Atala, A., 2019. Bladder organoids and spheroids: Potential tools for normal and diseased tissue modelling. *Anticancer Res.* 39, 1105–1118. <https://doi.org/10.21873/anticancer.13219>.
- Vyas, V., Solomon, M., D'Souza, G.G.M., Huey, B.D., 2019. Nanomechanical analysis of extracellular matrix and cells in multicellular spheroids. *Cell. Mol. Bioeng.* 12, 203–214. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12195-019-00577-0>.
- Wang, N., Zhang, M., Chang, Y., Niu, N., Guan, Y., Ye, M., Li, C., Tang, J., 2019. Directly observing alterations of morphology and mechanical properties of living cancer cells with atomic force microscopy. *Talanta* 191, 461–468. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.talanta.2018.09.008>.
- Wang, H., Zhang, H., Da, B., Lu, D., Tamura, R., Goto, K., Watanabe, I., Fujita, D., Hanagata, N., Kano, J., Nakagawa, T., Noguchi, M., 2021. Mechanomics biomarker for cancer cells unidentifiable through morphology and elastic modulus. *Nano Lett.* 21, 1538–1545. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.nanolett.1c00003>.
- Weder, G., Hendriks-Balk, M.C., Smajda, R., Rimoldi, D., Liley, M., Heinzelmann, H., Meister, A., Mariotti, A., 2014. Increased plasticity of the stiffness of melanoma cells correlates with their acquisition of metastatic properties. *Nanomed. Nanotechnol. Biol. Med.* 10, 141–148. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nano.2013.07.007>.
- Weiswald, L.B., Bellet, D., Dangles-Marie, V., 2015. Spherical cancer models in tumor biology. *Neoplasia (United States)* 17, 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neo.2014.12.004>.
- Wu, C.T., Chang, Y.H., Lin, P.Y., Chen, W.C., Chen, M.F., 2014. Thrombomodulin expression regulates tumorigenesis in bladder cancer. *BMC Cancer* 14, 375. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2407-14-375>.
- Xu, W., Mezenzev, R., Kim, B., Wang, L., McDonald, J., Sulchek, T., Batra, S.K., 2012. Cell stiffness is a biomarker of the metastatic potential of ovarian cancer cells. *PLoS ONE* 7 (10), e46609.
- Yamaguchi, H., Condeelis, J., 2007. Regulation of the actin cytoskeleton in cancer cell migration and invasion. *Biochim. Biophys. Acta - Mol. Cell Res.* 1773, 642–652. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bbamer.2006.07.001>.
- Zemla, J., Bobrowska, J., Kubiak, A., Zieliński, T., Pabijan, J., Pogoda, K., Bobrowski, P., Lekka, M., 2020. Indenting soft samples (hydrogels and cells) with cantilevers possessing various shapes of probing tip. *Eur. Biophys. J.* 49, 485–495. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00249-020-01456-7>.